

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Coordinated electrophoretic deposition of composite chitosan-layered double hydroxide coatings on AZ31 magnesium alloy

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The development of advanced biomedical materials is an urgent task to improve the life quality of people. One of the ways of the development of metallic implant materials is the creation of temporary implants, which allow to get rid of the requirement of secondary surgeries in traumatic cases since the implant is dissolved in the human body in a reasonable timeframe. However, to create such materials, it is important to precisely control their biodegradation rate and biocompatibility. For example, Mg and its alloys are promising metallic biodegradable materials, which, unfortunately, have high degradation rates. To control the degradation profile of Mg alloys, different types of surface treatment, like anodization, conversion and polymer coatings, are usually applied. Recently, special attention has been paid to so-called smart or self-healing coatings, which refer to the ability of the coating to repair itself or release active substances into the surrounding media under the influence of physical or chemical triggers.

Among self-healing materials, layered double hydroxides (LDHs) are especially promising due to their unique structure and ability to intercalate corrosion inhibitors. Implementation of such inhibitor carriers into biocompatible polymer matrices allows for the creation of surface layers with the control of the degradation profile and other properties in a wide range of parameters, like the amount of the inhibitor or active substance in the mixed inhibitor-antibiotic carriers. As a polymer matrix of such composites, chitosan can be used.

The main aim of the study was to develop a composite coating consisting of a chitosan matrix with LDH particles filled with different biocompatible corrosion inhibitors and/or antibacterial active substances on the surface of AZ31 Mg alloy. The deposition of coatings was done by cathodic electrophoretic approach utilizing two organic acids as coordination agents. The used MgAlNO₃ LDH particles were synthesized by a controlled precipitation approach. Three aging times were used for the development of particles with varied surface area and sorption capacity. The deposition of the coatings was performed from aqueous solutions containing 50% ethanol and chitosan of low, medium, and high molecular weight. Different current regimes and deposition times were tested. Characterization of the coatings included scanning electron microscopy, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, surface contact angle measurements, and Raman spectroscopy. The degradation profiles of the coatings were examined *in vitro* in Hank's solution. The dynamic and classical electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and hydrogen evolution tests were employed. The results confirmed the high effectiveness of the formed composites towards the improved corrosion resistance of the AZ31 alloy. The values of the low-frequency impedance modulus reached up to 150 kΩ cm² and were stable in time up to 14 days, showing high protective ability of the formed coatings on the initial stages of the degradation.

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